

1 **Molecular Phylogenetics and Taxonomy of the Andean Genus *Lynchius* Hedges, Heinicke,**
2 **and Duellman 2008 (Anura: Craugastoridae)**

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23 RRH: PHYLOGENETICS AND TAXONOMY OF *LYNCHIUS*
24

25 ABSTRACT: We infer species relationships within *Lynchius*, a frog genus with four
26 species distributed along the paramos and cloud forests of the Andes of northern Peru and
27 southern Ecuador, and assess species diversity in light of comparative analyses of anatomical
28 traits and inferred relationships. Phylogenetic analyses rely on ca. 7000 base pairs of mtDNA and
29 nuDNA sequences, aligned using similarity-alignment and tree-alignment, and optimized under
30 the maximum likelihood and parsimony criteria. Inferred relationships place *Lynchius* as the
31 sister group of the widespread genus *Oreobates*, and this clade as the sister group of the high
32 Andean genus *Phrynopus*. Our analyses corroborate the dissimilar species *Lynchius simmonsii* as
33 part of this clade, and place it as the sister group of the remaining species of *Lynchius*.
34 Parsimony and maximum likelihood analyses differ in the internal relationships of *Lynchius*,
35 with respect to the placement of *L. flavomaculatus*, *L. nebulanastes*, and *L. parkeri*, but support
36 the existence of two unnamed species. External morphological comparisons provide diagnostic
37 characters for the two new species, which are named and described herein. *Lynchius tabaconas* is
38 sister to *L. flavomaculatus* and occurs at ca. 2800 m in the cloud forests of Santuario Nacional
39 Tabaconas-Namballe, Cajamarca, Peru. *Lynchius oblitus* occurs in the same area but at higher
40 elevation (ca. 3300 m) and is sister to a clade formed by *L. flavomaculatus* and *L. tabaconas* in
41 parsimony analyses and to *L. nebulanastes* in maximum likelihood analyses. We provide a new
42 diagnosis for each of the six species and for the genus, as well as some natural history notes.

43

44 **Key words:** Brachycephaloidea; *Lynchius oblitus* sp. nov.; *Lynchius tabaconas* sp. nov.;

45 *Oreobates*; Paramo; *Phrynopus*; Terrarana.

46

47 THE WET and cold grasslands and elfin forests of the high Andes have been traditionally
48 considered poor in frogs' diversity. Recent surveys in northern Bolivia and in Peru have
49 nonetheless unraveled unexpected levels of new species of terrarana frogs in different lineages
50 (e.g., De la Riva 2007; Lehr and Catenazzi 2009; Lehr et al. 2012; Chaparro et al. 2015). Albeit
51 these high-elevation lineages have been historically considered part of the genus *Phrynopus*
52 (Lynch 1975), molecular data reveal a contrasting scenario where they have independent origins
53 (Heinicke et al. 2007; Hedges et al. 2008; Padial et al. 2014). According to inferred relationships,
54 species from Bolivia and southern Peru have been placed in the genera *Bryophryne*, *Noblella*,
55 and *Psychrophrynella*, the radiation in the Andes of central Peru retained the name *Phrynopus*,
56 and the genus *Lynchius* — target of this study — was erected to include three species distributed
57 along the paramos and elfin forests of the Cordillera Oriental in southern Ecuador and Cordillera
58 de Huancabamba in northern Peru (Hedges et al. 2008).

59 Along the Cordillera de Huancabamba in northern Peru and the southern parts of the
60 Cordillera Oriental of Ecuador the western slopes are mostly dry and covered by “chaparral-like”
61 forest, while the summit and eastern — Amazonian — versant are moist and covered with dense
62 vegetation. Above ca. 2000 m elevation on the eastern versant, dense cloud forests and bush-like
63 elfin forests and paramos gradually replace montane forests. *Lynchius flavomaculatus*, the first
64 species of *Lynchius* discovered, was found in the cloud forests and paramos of a locality 15 km
65 east of Loja (Ecuador) (Parker 1938), that is now part of the Podocarpus National Park, but it is
66 currently known to occur farther north and south within Ecuador. *Lynchius nebulanastes*
67 (Cannatella 1984) and *Lynchius parkeri* (Lynch 1975) were found in paramos and cloud forests,
68 even in syntopy, but farther south, along one of the westernmost ridges of the Peruvian
69 Cordillera de Huancabamba. A fourth but unnamed species is also known to occur in northern

70 Peru (Lehr 2005; Hedges et al. 2008; Padial et al. 2014), in the paramos and elfin forests of an
71 area intermediate between the southern distribution of *L. nebulanastes* and *L. parkeri* and the
72 northern distribution of *L. flavomaculatus*. A fifth, and quite morphologically dissimilar species,
73 *L. simmonsii* (Lynch 1974), was recently inferred as the sister group of *Lynchiuss*, and is now
74 considered part of this genus (Padial et al. 2012, 2014). In contrast to the fourth other species,
75 *Lynchiuss simmonsii* occurs at lower elevations (ca. 1800 m) along the cloud forests of the
76 Cordillera del Cndor, in Ecuador, on the easternmost ridges of the Amazonian versant of the
77 Andes.

78 *Lynchiuss* remains a poorly known Andean clade and, although its phylogenetic
79 relationships and osteology have been studied in some detail (e.g., Lynch 1975; Duellman and
80 Lehr 2009; Padial et al. 2014), several aspects of its systematics and natural history remain
81 scarcely studied. For example, morphological variation within this clade is poorly understood, as
82 species were described independently and comparisons were made within a now obsolete
83 phylogenetic framework (e.g., species of *Lynchiuss* were thought to be part of *Phrynopus*,
84 *Ischnocnema*, and *Oreobates*). After the inference of *Lynchiuss simmonsii* as part of this clade, the
85 patterns of distribution and morphological variation within the clade of *Lynchiuss* changed
86 considerably. Furthermore, the phylogenetic relationships of *Lynchiuss* remain contentious.
87 Molecular phylogenetic analyses have placed *Lynchiuss* as either the sister group of *Phrynopus*
88 (Padial et al. 2009), *Oreobates* (Hedges et al. 2008; Padial et al. 2014), or as the sister group of
89 *Oreobates* and *Phrynopus* (Padial et al. 2012).

90 Besides the undescribed species from northern Peru mentioned above, recent fieldwork in
91 this region and in southern Ecuador by some of the authors of this study revealed the existence of
92 another unnamed species of *Lynchiuss*, and provided additional material for comparison and more

93 rigorous phylogenetic analyses. Here, we present the results of our analyses of the external
94 morphology of all available specimens, and phylogenetic analyses of a matrix composed of
95 mtDNA genes (12S, 16S and intervening genes, cytb) and nuDNA genes (28S c-myc, H3,
96 POMC, Rag, Rho, SIA, and Tyr). Our analyses support the existence of the two aforementioned
97 new species, which are named and described herein. Furthermore, we provide an overview of
98 species diversity, current understanding of morphological variation within species, phylogenetic
99 relationships for the group, and some new natural history notes.

100

101 MATERIALS AND METHODS

102

Morphology

103

The study of the morphology is based on external qualitative and quantitative traits.

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Terminology for morphological characters used in the diagnosis and descriptions follows

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Duellman and Lehr (2009). For morphometrics, the measurements were taken with a digital

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caliper to the nearest 0.01 mm, but in order to avoid pseudo precision, all measurements were

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rounded to one decimal. All measurements were taken by the senior author except for *Lynchius*

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simmonsii. Measurements of the holotype of *O. simmonsii* were taken by J. Padial, while QCAZ

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vouchers were measured by ... Unfortunately not all measurements were taken by the different

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persons. Abbreviations for measurements are as follows: snout–vent length, SVL; head length

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(from posterior margin of lower jaw to tip of snout), HL; head width (measured at level of

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rictus), HW; eye length (measured horizontally), EL; eye to nostril distance, EN; internarial

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distance, IND; eye-eye distance (measured at the anterior margins of eyes), EE; tympanic

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membrane height, TYH; tympanic membrane length, TYL; width of disc of Finger III, F3; width

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of disc of Finger IV, F4; arm length (from posterior margin of thenar tubercle to elbow), FA;

116 tibia length, TL; thigh length (from vent to knee), TH; foot length (from proximal border of inner
117 metatarsal tubercle to tip of fourth toe), FL; width of disc of Toe IV, T4. Values of interorbital
118 distance (IOD) and upper eyelid width (EW) were not included due to the imprecise landmarks
119 of the structures involved, especially in poorly preserved specimens.

120 Descriptions of color patterns in life are based on field notes and color digital
121 photographs. Sex and maturity were determined by dissection and direct examination of gonads
122 or observation of secondary sexual characters. Comparisons of external character states were
123 based both on original descriptions and examination of museum specimens, including types.
124 Types of all species of *Lynchius* were examined.

125 Specimens collected were photographed alive, euthanized with anesthetics (Lidocaine),
126 fixed in 10% formalin, and preserved in 70% ethanol. Coordinates were obtained by means of a
127 Garmin PSMAP 62sc Handheld Navigator Global Positioning System (GPS), and further
128 assessments for geographical data and elevation were performed in Google Earth.

129 Museum acronyms are those cited by Frost (2016), except that MHNC refers to Museo de
130 Historia Natural de Cusco, Universidad Nacional de San Antonio Abad del Cusco, Cusco, Peru
131 (MHNCP in Frost 2016). Specimens examined are listed in Appendix I. All geographic
132 coordinates are based on geodetic datum WGS84.

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Molecular phylogenetics

135 **Taxon and character sampling.**—In order to rigorously test the phylogenetic position
136 and monophyly of *Lynchius*, we sampled the Holoadeninae genera *Oreobates* (22 spp.) and
137 *Phrynopus* (11 spp.) broadly, as these are the two genera that have been found most closely
138 related to *Lynchius* in all previous phylogenetic analyses (Pyron and Wiens 2011; Hedges et al.

139 2008; Padial et al. 2009; Padial et al. 2012; Padial et al. 2014). We also sampled Holoadeninae
140 (Padial et al. 2014) by including representatives of the genera *Barycholos* (2 spp.), *Bryophryne*
141 (1 spp.), *Euparkerella* (1 spp.), *Holoaden* (2 spp.), *Hypodactylus* (2 spp.), *Noblella* (3 spp.), and
142 *Psychrophrynella* (3 spp.). Ingroup sampling includes four terminals representing all four
143 nominal species of *Lynchius*, plus eight terminals that were not part of any nominal species.
144 *Haddadus binotatus*, a distant craugastorid of the Craugastorinae (Padial et al. 2014), was used
145 to root the trees.

146 Our matrix includes legacy (GenBank) and newly produced sequences for 16 genes. Non-
147 coding mtDNA genes include rRNA genes of the heavy strand transcription unit 1 fragment
148 (12S, 16S and the intervening tRNA^{valine}, and tRNA^{leucine} segments). Protein-coding mtDNA
149 genes include cytochrome b (cytb). Nuclear protein-coding genes include two exons of cellular
150 myelocytomatosis (c-myc), histone H3 (HH3), proopiomelanocortin A (POMC), recombination-
151 activating protein 1 (RAG1), rhodopsin (Rhod), seven-in-absentia (SIA), and tyrosinase
152 precursor (Tyr). Non-coding nuclear genes include 28S. Sequences for 12S, 16S, tRNA^{valine},
153 tRNA^{leucine}, POMC, RAG, and TYR genes were newly produced for this study. Specimen
154 voucher numbers and locality data for sequences produced in this study are listed in Table 1.
155 Accession numbers for all sequences used in this study are listed in Appendix II.

156
157 **DNA amplification and sequencing.**—Genomic DNA was extracted from ethanol-
158 preserved tissues using standard phenol-chloroform extraction protocols. The standard
159 polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification protocol was as follows: 95°C/15 s; 35 cycles of
160 95°C/30 s, 50°C/ 30 s, 72°C/1 min; and 72°C/10 min. Cycle sequencing reactions were
161 completed using the corresponding PCR primers (Table 2) and BigDye Terminator 3.1 chemistry

162 (Applied Biosciences), with a standard cycle sequencing profile (96°C/3 min; 35 cycles of
163 96°C/10 s, 50°C/15 s, 60°C/3 min; and 72°C/7 min). PCR products were visualized in agarose
164 gels, and unincorporated primers and dNTPs were removed from PCR products using ExoSap
165 purification (ExoSap-it, GE Healthcare). Double stranded DNA was sequenced in Macrogen.
166 Raw sequences complementary strands were compared to generate a consensus sequence for
167 each DNA fragment using Geneious 7.0 (Biomatters Ltd.)

168

169 Phylogenetic analyses

170 **Parsimony analysis.**—Sequences were first aligned in MAFFT (see below) and
171 partitioned into fragments of equal length separated by conserved regions with no gaps and few
172 or no nucleotide substitutions. This strategy generated putatively homologous fragments where
173 length variation among DNA sequences was only due to insertions and/or deletions of
174 nucleotides, a requisite for tree-alignment in POY (Wheeler et al. 2006). After the removal of
175 gaps implied by MAFFT from sequence fragments, tree-alignment of unaligned sequences was
176 performed under parsimony with equal weights for all classes of transformations using direct
177 optimization (DO; Wheeler 1996; Wheeler et al. 2006) and iterative pass optimization (IPO;
178 Wheeler 2003) algorithms in POY 5.1.1 (Varón et al. 2010). Tree searches were first conducted
179 using DO under the command “search”, which implements an algorithm based on random
180 addition sequence Wagner builds, subtree pruning and regrafting, and tree bisection and
181 reconnection branch swapping (see Goloboff 1996, 1999), parsimony ratcheting (Nixon 1999),
182 and tree fusing (Goloboff 1999); then, consecutive rounds of searches are done within a specified
183 run-time, storing the shortest trees of each independent run and performing a final round of tree-
184 fusing on the pooled trees. The optimal tree found during driven searches was swapped using

185 iterative pass optimization (Wheeler 2003). Tree searches were carried out using the American
186 Museum of Natural History's high performance computing cluster ENYO (a cluster of 33 Intel
187 Xeon 3.0GHz dual-core, 128 dual-processors, L2 cache, 64-bit and 1TB shared storage, and
188 16GB RAM per node). As we have observed that POY 4.1.2 or POY 5.1.1 does not always
189 report all equally parsimonious trees when large datasets are analyzed, the optimal alignment
190 resulting from iterative pass optimization was converted into a data matrix, and driven searches
191 were conducted in TNT (Goloboff et al. 2008) until a stable strict consensus was reached at least
192 three times (see below for details of driven searches in TNT). We calculated Goodman-Bremer
193 (GB) values (Bremer 1988; Goodman et al. 1982; see Grant and Kluge 2008) for each supported
194 clade in TNT using the optimal tree-alignment matrix and the parameters specified in the
195 bremer.run macro (available with the software package at
196 <http://www.zmuc.dk/public/phylogeny/tnt/>), which begins by searching for trees N steps longer
197 than the optimum (10 random addition sequence Wagner builds and TBR swapping, saving two
198 trees per replicate), using inverse constraints for each node of the most parsimonious tree.
199 Swapping of each constrained search was limited to 20 minutes and constrained searches were
200 repeated three times as specified in the default settings of the bremer.run macro. We also
201 calculated parsimony jackknife frequencies (Farris et al. 1996) for each supported clade by
202 resampling the tree-alignment matrix. We caution that, as in analyses of similarity-alignment
203 matrices, the resulting clade frequencies are conditional on this particular alignment and not the
204 data themselves. Given that the tree-alignment matrix is derived from the optimal tree, the
205 resulting clade frequencies are expected to be higher than would be obtained from matrices
206 aligned according to different guide trees (*e.g.*, a UPGMA or neighbor-joining tree, as in
207 MAFFT and Clustal, respectively). We calculated jackknife frequencies from 1000

208 pseudoreplicates searches using driven searches (see below), gaps treated as fifth state, and
209 removal probability of 0.36 ($\approx e^{-1}$), which purportedly renders jackknife and bootstrap values
210 comparable (Farris et al. 1996).

211

212 **Maximum likelihood.**—Multiple sequence alignments for maximum-likelihood analyses
213 were performed in MAFFT online version 7 using the G-INS-i strategy, which is considered
214 appropriate for alignments that consist of large numbers of sequences (Kato and Standley 2013;
215 Kato et al. 2005). The G-INS-i strategy performs global alignment with a Fast Fourier
216 Transform (FFT) approximation progressively on a guide tree (modified UPGMA) followed by
217 iterative edge refinement that evaluates the consistency between the multiple alignment and
218 pairwise alignments. The iterative refinement is repeated until no improvement is observed in the
219 weighted sum-of-pairs score or 1000 cycles are completed (maxiterate = 1000). We applied the
220 default transition/transversion cost ratio of 1:2 but changed the gap opening penalty from 3 times
221 substitutions to 1 time substitutions to avoid penalizing insertions and deletions more than we did
222 in the parsimony analysis.

223 We used PartitionFinder V1.0.1 (Lanfear et al. 2012) to select the optimal partition
224 scheme and substitution models for our dataset under the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC),
225 the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and the Corrected Akaike Information Criterion
226 (cAIC). Compared partition schemes were: (1) all data combined, (2) a 2-partition,
227 mtDNA/nuDNA, scheme, (3) by locus (each partition corresponding to individual loci
228 mentioned above), and (4), by locus and codon position (for protein coding genes).

229 Adaptive maximum-likelihood tree searches and 1000 bootstrap replicates were
230 performed using random addition sequence replicates in GARLI 2.0 (Zwickl 2006) through the

254 shown as Fig. 1A).

255 The optimal MAFFT similarity-alignment comprises 7145 character columns. The AIC,
256 AICc, and BIC in Partition Finder identified the 2-partition (mtDNA/nuDNA) scheme with GTR
257 + I + G substitution model for coding and non-coding mtDNA and TIM+I+G for nuDNA as the
258 most optimal partition scheme (values for the different information criteria, AIC: 109085.32854;
259 AICc: 109084.97898; BIC: 110820.623499). Under the selected partition scheme and
260 substitution models, the best maximum likelihood was found once during 10 adaptive searches in
261 GARLI (maximum likelihood score of the optimal tree = -54,289.266; Fig. 1B).

262 Parsimony and maximum likelihood character optimizations recover a monophyletic
263 *Lynchius* as the sister group of *Oreobates*. These two monophyletic genera form the sister group
264 of *Phrynopus*. Within *Lynchius*, parsimony and maximum likelihood recover *L. simmonsii* as the
265 sister group of the remaining species. Also, both analyses recover one of the new species
266 (*Lynchius tabaconas*) as the sister group of *L. flavomaculatus* (separated by uncorrected p-
267 distances of 6.0%; Table 3). However, the position of *L. nebulanastes* and *L. parkeri* differ
268 between the two analyses. Parsimony recovers *L. oblitus* as the sister group of *L. flavomaculatus*
269 plus *L. tabaconas*, while it is the sister group of *L. parkeri* in maximum likelihood (separated by
270 uncorrected p-distances of 9–10%; Table 3). Regardless of these discrepancies, both analyses
271 support the monophyly of the two new species.

272 Within *Phrynopus*, most relationships are identical between the two analyses, but differ
273 with respect to the position of *P. auriculatus*, *P. heimorum* and *P. tribulosus*. Several
274 relationships also differ among species of *Oreobates*. *Oreobates ayacucho* is the sister species of
275 *O. lehri*, *O. machigenga*, and *O. gemcare* in parsimony, while it is sister to *O. lundbergi* and *O.*
276 *pereger* in maximum likelihood. Also, *O. remotus* is the sister species of *O. berdemenos* in

277 parsimony and of *O. crepitans* in maximum likelihood. *Oreobates heterodactylus* and *O.*
 278 *crepitans* are sister in parsimony, while *O. heterodactylus* is the sister species of *O. berdemenos*
 279 in maximum likelihood. Also, while *O. discoidailis* and *O. barituensis* are sister in parsimony,
 280 the later is sister to *O. ibischi* in maximum likelihood.

281 Within the rest of outgroups there are differences in the position of *Bryophryne*,
 282 *Hypodactylus*, and *Psychrophrynella*. *Bryophryne* is recovered as the sister group of *Barycholos*
 283 and *Noblella* in parsimony, while it is sister of *Euparkerella* and *Holoaden* in maximum
 284 likelihood. *Hypodactylus* is recovered as paraphyletic near the root of the tree in maximum
 285 likelihood analyses, while it is recovered as the sister group of the clade that includes *Lynchius*,
 286 *Oreobates*, and *Phrynopus* in parsimony analyses. *Psychrophrynella* is found as the sister group
 287 of a clade that includes *Hypodactylus*, *Lynchius*, *Oreobates*, and *Phrynopus* in parsimony, while
 288 it is the sister of a clade that includes *Barycholos*, *Bryophryne*, *Euparkerella*, *Holoaden*, and
 289 *Noblella* in maximum likelihood. It is important to consider, however, that type species of the
 290 genera *Noblella* and *Psychrophrynella* have not yet been included in any molecular phylogenetic
 291 analysis and, therefore, the monophyly of these two genera remains to be tested.

292

293

SYSTEMATIC ACCOUNTS

294

Lynchius Hedges, Heinicke, and Duellman, 2008

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Diagnosis.—The genus *Lynchius* includes species with the following characteristics: skin
 on dorsum of head, body, and limbs shagreen with few scattered tubercles, covered with
 uniform-sized spicule-like warts in *L. simmonsii*; occipital folds \wedge or \vee -shaped, when present;
 middorsal fold present; dorsolateral fold present or absent; venter smooth to areolate; discoidal
 fold present; tympanic membrane and annulus distinct or indistinct; supratympanic fold and

300 postrictal tubercles present or absent; head as long as wide or slightly longer than wide; snout
 301 round to nearly truncate in dorsal view, and rounded or curved anteroventrally in lateral profile;
 302 canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view; cranial crests present or absent; upper eyelid
 303 with or without small, scattered tubercles; dentigerous process of the vomers prominent, slightly
 304 oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae, each process bearing 2–8 teeth; males without
 305 nuptial pads, vocal slits present or absent; first finger as long as, shorter, or longer than second;
 306 subarticular tubercles prominent, round or conical; supernumerary tubercles round, smaller than
 307 subarticular tubercles; tips of fingers narrowly round; pads, circumferential grooves, lateral
 308 fringes, and hand webbing usually absent (present on Fingers I and II in *L. flavomaculatus*);
 309 ulnar tubercle absent; palmar tubercle rounded or divided in two subunits; thenar tubercle
 310 prominent, elliptical; foot length 42–60% SVL; Toe III longer than Toe V; tips of toes narrowly
 311 rounded, lacking pads and circumferential grooves; toe lateral fringes and webbing absent; inner
 312 metatarsal tubercle elongate, prominent; outer metatarsal tubercle round, prominent, slightly
 313 smaller or about the same size as inner; heel and tarsal tubercles absent; frontoparietals with or
 314 without exostosis; vomers bearing a broad dentigerous process, widely separated from each
 315 other, and bearing a row of teeth. Reproduction by terrestrial eggs and direct-development.

316

317 **Content.**—*Lynchius flavomaculatus* (Parker, 1938), *L. nebulanastes* (Cannatella, 1984),
 318 *L. oblitus*, *L. parkeri* (Lynch, 1975), *L. simmonsii* (Lynch, 1974), and *L. tabaconas*.

319

320 **Distribution.**—Montane forests, cloud forests, and paramos of the Andes of Peru and
 321 Ecuador, along the Cordillera de Huancabamba, Cordillera del Cóndor, and Cordillera Oriental
 322 at elevations between 1800 and 3300 m.

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324

Lynchius flavomaculatus (Parker, 1938)

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(Figs. 2A–B)

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Eleutherodactylus flavomaculatus: Parker, 1938

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Niceforonia flavomaculata: Lynch, 1969

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Phrynopus flavomaculatus: Lynch, 1975

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Eleutherodactylus flavomaculatus: Lehr, 2006

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"Eleutherodactylus" flavomaculatus: Heinicke et al., 2007

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Lynchius flavomaculatus: Hedges et al., 2008

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333

Holotype.—BMNH 1947.2.16.11 (formerly 1935.11.3.16), adult female from 15 km East

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of Loja City, Ecuador, 3100 m, collected by C. Carrión (Figs. 2A–B).

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336

Diagnosis.—A large *Lynchius* (SVL of adult females 34.6–44.2 mm, n = 31; adult males

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24.0–35.2 mm, n = 27) characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and limbs

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shagreen, with few scattered tubercles that are more abundant posteriorly; occipital folds absent;

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middorsal fold complete or incomplete when present; dorsolateral folds absent; venter smooth to

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weakly areolate; groin smooth; discoidal and thoracic folds present; (2) tympanic membrane and

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annulus distinct, its diameter 42–53% of eye diameter; supratympanic fold low; postrictal

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tubercles present; (3) head as long as wide or slightly longer than wide (HW/HL 0.9–1.0); snout

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round in dorsal and lateral views; canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view; loreal region

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concave, sloping gradually towards the lips; lips not flared; (4) cranial crests present; upper

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eyelid covered by small scattered tubercles; (5) dentigerous process of vomers prominent,

346 slightly oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae, each process bearing 5–6 teeth; (6) males
347 with vocal slits on each side of the tongue and no nuptial pads; (7) fingers long and slender, first
348 finger as long as second; subarticular tubercles prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles
349 round, smaller than subarticular tubercles; tips of fingers narrowly round; pads present in fingers
350 I and II; circumferential grooves, lateral fringes, and hand webbing absent; (8) ulnar tubercle
351 absent; (9) palmar tubercle divided in two subunits, the inner subunit much larger than the outer;
352 thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length about 50% SVL, lateral fringes and
353 webbing absent; Toe III longer than Toe V; Toe III usually reaching the distal border of second
354 subarticular tubercle of Toe IV, Toe V reaching the proximal border of second subarticular
355 tubercle of Toe IV; subarticular tubercles prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles absent; tips
356 of toes narrowly rounded, lacking pads and circumferential grooves; (11) inner metatarsal
357 tubercle elongate, prominent; outer metatarsal tubercle slightly smaller, round, prominent;
358 subarticular tubercles round, prominent; supernumerary tubercles absent; (12) heel and tarsal
359 tubercles absent; (13) in life, dorsum mottled dark yellow and reddish brown with indistinct
360 yellow bars on limbs, head and upper lips; dark brown transversal bars on limbs; flanks yellow
361 with brown spots; venter grayish brown, belly with conspicuous yellow blotches, also present on
362 ventral surfaces of limbs; yellow blotches on groin and anterior surfaces of thighs; fingers I and
363 II yellow dorsally and ventrally; iris pale green with black reticulations; in preservative, dorsum
364 dark brown with a light brown spotted pattern; indistinct cream bars on limbs and upper lips;
365 interorbital bar light brown, when present; some specimens with a cream middorsal stripe
366 extending to posterior surface of thigh; throat and belly brown; belly with conspicuous cream
367 blotches (yellow in life), in some specimens coalescing completely, turning belly uniformly
368 cream; cream blotches on groin and ventral surface of limbs; Fingers I and II white.

369

370 **Distribution and ecology.**—*Lynchi* *flavomaculatus* is known to occur in paramos at
371 2215–3100 m on the Cordillera Occidental in southeastern Ecuador (provinces of Loja, Zamora-
372 Chinchipe, and Morona-Santiago) (Fig. 3). Lehr (2006) recorded one specimen from the Río
373 Blanco Basin (3100 m) in Province of Huancabamba, Department of Piura, Peru. This species is
374 a terrestrial dweller occurring in grasslands of the Paramo ecoregion (Lynch 1975; Duellman and
375 Lehr 2009). Females produce large unpigmented eggs, indicating that they undergo direct
376 development without larval phase (Lynch 1969).

377

378 **Remarks.**—Parker (1938) provided an accurate description of the holotype and also
379 described the intraspecific variation, especially regarding coloration. He described the skin as
380 smooth in ventral and dorsal surfaces, although our observations indicate otherwise (see
381 diagnoses). Lynch (1969) noted that males lack nuptial pads, while Lehr (2006) mentioned the
382 presence of nuptial pads in males. Our re-examination of specimens (including KU119737, the
383 specimen in Fig. 6, p. 339 of Lehr 2006) failed to find nuptial pads. However, it is important to
384 point out that differences in character states such as skin texture, nuptial pads or circumferential
385 grooves may be due to poor preservation. Lynch (1975) provided a brief description of the
386 cranial osteology (only four characters), and a drawing of the skull in dorsal view. Duellman and
387 Lehr (2009) list the discoidal fold as absent and eyelid as lacking tubercles, but our examination
388 of specimens (listed in Appendix I) indicates otherwise. They also provide a picture of a live
389 specimen from the type locality (Fig. 71, p. 87).

390

391

Lynchi *nebulanastes* (Cannatella, 1984)

(Figs. 2C–D)

Phrynopus nebulanastes: Cannatella, 1984

Eleutherodactylus nebulanastes: Lehr, 2005

"*Eleutherodactylus*" *nebulanastes*: Heinicke et al., 2007

Lynchius nebulanastes: Hedges et al., 2008

397

Holotype.—KU 181407, adult female from El Tambo, 31.5 km East of Conchaque, 2700 m, Departamento Piura, Peru (Figs. 2C–D), collected by T. J. Berger, D. C. Cannatella, and W. E. Duellman on 27 February 1979 (Fig. 72 in Duellman and Lehr 2009).

401

Diagnosis.—A moderately large species of *Lynchius* (SVL of adult females 34.5–40.7 mm, n = 10; adult males 27.0–35.8 mm, n = 10) characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and limbs shagreen, with scattered tubercles, more abundant posteriorly; shanks bearing abundant small tubercles, in some specimens larger and wart-like; occipital folds absent; middorsal fold from the end of head to cloacal region; lateral folds present; dorsolateral fold long and discontinuous; venter and groin smooth; discoidal and thoracic folds present; (2) tympanic membrane and annulus indistinct; supratympanic fold low, extending behind the tympanic region; postrictal tubercles present, in a row; (3) head as long as wide or slightly longer than wide (HW/HL 0.9–1.0); snout short, round in dorsal and lateral views; canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view; (4) cranial crests absent; upper eyelid covered by small scattered tubercles; (5) dentigerous process of vomers prominent, slightly oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae, each process bearing 3–5 teeth; (6) males lacking vocal slits and nuptial pads; (7) fingers long and slender, first finger as long as second; subarticular tubercles prominent, round;

415 supernumerary tubercles large, round, smaller than subarticular tubercles; tips of fingers
416 narrowly round; pads, circumferential grooves, lateral fringes, and hand webbing absent; (8)
417 ulnar tubercle absent; (9) palmar tubercle divided in two subunits, inner subunit much larger than
418 outer; thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length 50–60% SVL, lateral fringes and
419 foot webbing absent; Toe III longer than Toe V; Toe III usually reaching distal margin of second
420 subarticular tubercle of Toe IV, Toe V reaching middle of second subarticular tubercle of Toe
421 IV; subarticular tubercles prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles absent; tips of toes
422 narrowly rounded, lacking pads and circumferential grooves; (11) inner metatarsal tubercle
423 elongate, prominent; outer metatarsal tubercle smaller, round, prominent; subarticular tubercles
424 round, prominent; supernumerary tubercles absent; (12) heel and tarsal tubercles absent; (13) in
425 life, dorsum brown, reddish brown or dark green; some specimens with cream middorsal stripe
426 extending to posterior surface of thigh and shank, sometimes reaching plantar surface; flanks
427 cream with black mottling; limbs light brown; canthus rostralis dark brown to black; light brown
428 bar parallel to upper lip; venter greenish yellow with brown or gray mottling; ventral surfaces of
429 limbs and spots on groin and thighs bright yellow; iris dull bronze; in preservative, dorsum
430 brown with black and pale spots; canthus rostralis dark brown; belly cream; throat light brown to
431 pale.

432

433 **Distribution and ecology.**—*Lynchius nebulanastes* occurs in humid forests from 2779 to
434 2820 m elevation on the western slopes of the Cordillera de Huancabamba (Fig. 3). According to
435 Cannatella (1984), specimens were found under rocks in disturbed elfin forests, and the male
436 advertisement call sounds like a “tick-tick-tick”.

437

461 *Lynchius* sp.: Hedges et al., 2008

462 *Lynchius* sp.: Padial et al., 2014

463

464 **Holotype.**— MHNC 8674, an adult female from Quebrada del Vino, 22 km West from
465 San Ignacio, inside of National Sanctuary of Tabaconas-Namballe (NSTN), District Namballe,
466 Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 3270 m (5°14'15.10"S, 79°16'48.65"W)
467 (Figs. 4, 5), collected by A. Pari and K. Pino, on 26 October 2009.

468

469 **Paratypes.**— Five adult males: MHNC 8614 from Laguna Victoria (NSTN), District
470 Tabaconas, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 3297 m (5°13'45.25"S,
471 79°17'13.57"W), collected by J. Delgado, on 05 October 2009; MHNC 8652 from Quebrada del
472 Vino, 22 km West from San Ignacio (NSTN), District Namballe, Province San Ignacio,
473 Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 2950 m (5°09'53.31"S, 79°12'4.56"W), collected by J.C.
474 Chaparro, on 18 October 2009; MHNC 8676 from Quebrada del Vino, 22 km West from San
475 Ignacio (NSTN), District Namballe, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 3270
476 m (5°14'15.10"S, 79°16'48.65"W), collected by A. Pari and K. Pino, on 07 October 2009;
477 MHNSM 19914 and MTD 45954 from Lagunas Arrebiatadas (NSTN), Province San Ignacio,
478 Department of Cajamarca, Peru. Three adult females: MHNC 8601 (Fig. 6) from Laguna
479 Victoria (NSTN), District Tabaconas, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru,
480 3291 m (5°14'15.10"S, 79°16'48.65"W), collected by J. Delgado, on 04 October 2009; MHNC
481 8675 and MHNC 8677 from Quebrada del Vino, 22 km West from San Ignacio (NSTN), District
482 Namballe, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 3291 m (5°14'15.10"S,
483 79°16'48.65"W), collected by A. Pari and K. Pino, on 07 October 2009.

484

485 **Referred specimens.**—Six specimens: MHNC 8598–8599, MHNC 8602, MHNC 8606,
486 MHNC 8625–8626 from the same locality and data than paratype MHNC 8614. Four specimens:
487 MHNC8672–8673, MHNC8689–8690 from Quebrada del Vino, 22 km West from San Ignacio
488 (NSTN), District Namballe, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 2950 m
489 (5°9'53.31"S, 79°12'4.56"W), collected by J.C. Chaparro, on 17 October 2009.

490

491 **Diagnosis.**—A small *Lynchius* (SVL of adult females 24.5–28.4 mm, n = 4; adult male
492 21.7 mm; see Table 4), characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and limbs
493 shagreen, with few scattered tubercles; occipital folds V-shaped; middorsal fold present;
494 middorsum bearing folds < >-shaped or w-shaped; dorsolateral folds long and discontinuous;
495 venter smooth; groin smooth; discoidal and thoracic folds present; (2) tympanic membrane and
496 annulus distinct, its diameter 45–56% of eye diameter; supratympanic fold poorly defined;
497 postrictal tubercles absent; (3) head as long as wide or slightly longer than wide (HW/HL 1.0);
498 snout broadly rounded in dorsal view and curved anteroventrally in lateral profile; canthus
499 rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view; (4) cranial crests present; upper eyelid without
500 tubercles; (5) dentigerous process of vomers prominent, slightly oblique, situated posteromedial
501 to choanae, each process bearing 2–3 teeth; (6) males lacking vocal slits and nuptial pads; (7)
502 hands with short fingers, first finger as long as or shorter than second; subarticular tubercles
503 prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles present; tips of fingers narrowly round; pads,
504 circumferential grooves, lateral fringes, and hand webbing absent; (8) ulnar tubercle absent; (9)
505 palmar tubercle divided in two subunits, inner subunit much larger than outer; thenar tubercle
506 prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length about 45% SVL; lateral fringes and toe webbing absent;

507 Toe III longer than Toe V; Toe III usually reaching middle of second subarticular tubercle of Toe
508 IV, Toe V reaching proximal border of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV; subarticular
509 tubercles low, round; supernumerary tubercles absent; tips of toes narrowly rounded, lacking
510 pads and circumferential grooves; (11) inner metatarsal tubercle elongate, prominent; outer
511 metatarsal tubercle round, about the same size as inner; subarticular tubercles round, low;
512 supernumerary tubercles absent; (12) heel and tarsal tubercles absent; (13) in preservative, dorsal
513 surfaces brown; light brown < >-shaped or w-shaped occipital mark; canthus rostralis dark
514 brown, a dark brown stripe posterior to eyes; hind limbs brown with dark brown bars; throat
515 cream with brown mottling or uniformly cream; belly and ventral surfaces of limbs cream with
516 dark brown blotches. Coloration in life (based on MHNC 8601) follows the same pattern
517 observed in specimens in preservative. However, in life the cream areas are yellowish, dorsal
518 surfaces are light brown to orange, and dorsal marks are cream and surrounded by dark brown.
519 Iris greenish brown with dark brown reticulations.

520

521 **Comparisons.**—*Lynchius oblitus* differs from all other species of *Lynchius* by the
522 following unique combination of characters: dorsum with occipital folds; < >-shaped or W-
523 shaped folds on middorsum; tympanic membrane and annulus distinct; cranial crests present;
524 lateral fringes and webbing on fingers and toes absent; ventral surfaces with cream mottling; a
525 dark brown stripe posterior to eye. The new species differs from *L. flavomaculatus* (characters of
526 this and other species in parentheses) by its smaller size (SVL of females 34.6–44.2 mm; males
527 24.0–35.2 mm) and by bearing occipital folds and folds on middorsum (absent). *Lynchius oblitus*
528 can be distinguished from *L. nebulanastes* and *L. parkeri* by having a distinct tympanum
529 (indistinct), cranial crests (absent), yellow mottling on venter (absent), and by bearing occipital

530 folds and folds on middorsum (absent). From *L. simmonsii*, it differs by its smaller size (SVL of
531 females 35.0–40.1 mm; male 28.3 mm), rounded plantar tubercles (conical), skin on dorsum
532 shagreen with scattered tubercles (dorsum covered with uniform-sized spicule-like warts),
533 occipital and dorsolateral folds (absent), folds on middorsum (absent), lateral fringes on fingers
534 and toes absent (present), and yellow mottling on venter (venter brown). From *Lynchius*
535 *tabaconas* sp. nov., *L. oblitus* differs by having occipital folds, folds on middorsum, and cranial
536 crests (absent).

537

538 **Description of holotype.**—Head as long as wide (head width/head length = 1.0); snout
539 rounded in dorsal view and curved anteroventrally in lateral profile; nostrils not protuberant,
540 oriented laterally; canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view, round in frontal profile; loreal
541 region concave; lips not flared; upper eyelid with few small granules; cranial crests present.
542 Supratympanic fold weakly distinct; tympanic membrane and annulus distinct; tympanic
543 membrane nearly round, its length more than half of eye length; postriotal tubercles absent.
544 Choanae not concealed by palatal shelf of the maxillary arch when roof of mouth is viewed from
545 below; choanae small, round, separated by a distance equal to six times the diameter of choanae;
546 dentigerous process of the vomers prominent, oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae
547 (posterior margin at level of choanae), their width about two times diameter of choanae, bearing
548 2 or 3 vomerine teeth. Skin of dorsal surfaces shagreen, with few scattered tubercles on dorsum;
549 ventral surfaces smooth; thighs coarsely areolate posteriorly in ventral view; occipital fold V-
550 shaped; middorsum bearing folds <->-shaped; dorsolateral folds present, complete; discoidal fold
551 poorly defined; thoracic fold present. Ulnar tubercle absent; palmar tubercle completely divided
552 in two subunits, inner subunit much larger than outer; thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical;

553 subarticular tubercles round, larger than supernumerary tubercles; finger tips narrowly rounded;
 554 pads weakly present, circumferential grooves absent; fingers lacking lateral fringes and webbing;
 555 relative length of fingers: I<II<III>IV. Foot length 45% of SVL; heel and tarsus lacking
 556 tubercles or folds; inner metatarsal tubercle oval, prominent, larger than outer metatarsal
 557 tubercle; outer metatarsal tubercle round; toes lacking lateral fringes and webbing; toe tips
 558 narrowly rounded; pads and circumferential grooves absent; relative length of toes
 559 I<II<III>V<IV; Toe V reaching proximal margin of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV, and
 560 Toe III reaching its middle. In preservative, dorsal surfaces brown, a cream <>-shaped occipital
 561 mark; head as dorsum, canthus rostralis dark brown, almost black; dark brown stripes posterior
 562 to eye. Hind limbs brown with dark brown bars; forelimbs light brown with dark brown spots.
 563 Throat and belly brown with cream mottling; ventral surfaces of limbs dark brown with cream
 564 blotches that run together on thighs and forelimbs.

565

566 **Variation.**—The only male examined (MTD 45954) has a brown venter with few cream
 567 dots, cream mottling posterior to eyes, and hind limbs brown without bars. For variation in
 568 measurements, see Table 4.

569

570 **Etymology.**—The specific epithet “oblitus”, a Latin word meaning forgotten, neglected,
 571 refers to the fact that this species has been known to exist for ten years, but was not named and
 572 described until now. We wish to highlight the fact that an increasing number of species is being
 573 labeled as candidate species while their formal descriptions are neglected or postponed,
 574 hampering the incorporation of these species into empirical analyses of species diversity,
 575 evolution, and conservation.

599 *Phrynopus parkeri* Lynch, 1975

600 *Lynchiu*s *parkeri*: Hedges et al., 2008

601

602 **Holotype**.—KU 135278, adult male from the summit of the cordillera between
603 Canchaque and Huancabamba, Departamento of Piura, Peru, 3100 m (Figs. 2E–F), collected by
604 Thomas H. and P.R. Fritts on 11 May 1970.

605

606 **Diagnosis**.—A small *Lynchiu*s (SVL of adult females 24.9–34.5 mm, n = 40; adult males
607 21.1–28.3 mm, n = 35) characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and limbs
608 shagreen, with few scattered tubercles; shank with transversal folds; occipital folds ^-shaped,
609 when present; middorsal and dorsolateral folds long and discontinuous; when present; venter
610 smooth to weakly areolate; discoidal and thoracic folds present; (2) tympanic membrane and
611 annulus indistinct; supratympanic fold poorly defined; postrictal tubercles present, forming a low
612 row; (3) head as long as wide or slightly longer than wide (HW/HL 0.9–1.0); snout round in
613 dorsal and lateral views; canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view; (4) cranial crests
614 absent; upper eyelid tubercles absent; (5) dentigerous process of vomers prominent, slightly
615 oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae, each process bearing 2–4 teeth; (6) males lacking
616 vocal slits and nuptial pads; (7) hands with long and slender fingers, first finger as long as or
617 shorter than second; subarticular tubercles prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles round,
618 smaller than subarticular tubercles; tips of fingers narrowly round; pads, circumferential grooves,
619 lateral fringes, and hand webbing absent; (8) ulnar tubercle absent; (9) palmar tubercle
620 completely divided in two subunits, inner subunit much larger than outer; thenar tubercle
621 prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length 42–51% SVL, lateral fringes and webbing absent; Toe III

622 longer than Toe V; Toe III usually reaching distal margin of second subarticular tubercle of Toe
623 IV, Toe V reaching middle of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV; subarticular tubercles
624 prominent, round; supernumerary tubercles present; tips of toes narrowly rounded, lacking pads
625 and circumferential grooves; (11) inner metatarsal tubercle elongate, prominent; outer metatarsal
626 tubercle round, prominent, about the same size as inner; subarticular tubercles round, prominent;
627 supernumerary tubercles usually absent; (12) heel and tarsal tubercles absent; (13) in life, dorsum
628 coloration gray, reddish or grayish brown, or dark brown; flanks dark brown with metallic green
629 mottling; posterior surfaces of thighs dark brown to black with yellow spots and blotches; venter
630 dark gray to black with large yellow blotches on belly in males, yellow with brown reticulations
631 on belly in females; canthus rostralis dark brown; cream labial stripe present; iris dark brown; in
632 preservative, dorsum light brown to grayish brown; dorsum usually lighter than flanks; some
633 specimens with two cream dorsal bars on middorsum; light brown bar parallel to upper lip; belly
634 cream mottled with brown; throat light brown; some specimens with a middorsal stripe
635 extending to posterior surface of thigh and shank, sometimes reaching plantar surface.

636

637 **Distribution and ecology.**—*Lynchius parkeri* is known at elevations from 2700 to 3100
638 m on the Cordillera de Huancabamba in Peru (Fig. 3). It occurs in cloud forests and paramos,
639 where it has been found under rocks and within low vegetation. The advertisement call is a soft
640 chirp (Duellman and Lehr 2009).

641

642 **Remarks.**—Lynch (1975) provides an accurate description of this species, but our
643 diagnosis presents a larger number of characters and differs from the original description in that
644 we report dorsal skin texture as shagreen. However, it is important to point out that differences in

645 character states such as skin texture, nuptial pads or circumferential grooves may be due to poor
 646 preservation. Also, according to the original description, *L. parkeri* presents a tympanum
 647 concealed by skin. Lynch (1975) described males as having vocal slits and subgular vocal sac,
 648 while Cannatella (1984) failed to find vocal slits. Our observations also failed to find vocal slits.
 649 Lehr (2006) noted that males have nuptial pads, but we observed that both males and females
 650 present some rugosity on the dorsal surface of Finger I that does not constitute glandular tissue
 651 (observation based on specimens listed in Appendix I). Lynch (1975) presented a brief
 652 description of cranial osteology and a drawing of the skull in dorsal view. He considered the
 653 frontoparietals as lacking rugosities, and they are shown as smooth on the drawing (Lynch, 1975,
 654 p. 26, Fig. 10). However, Cannatella (1984) found the frontoparietals to be rugose, an
 655 observation that agrees with our examination of the skull of two specimens (KU 135306 and KU
 656 181824; Fig. 7).

657

658 *Lynchiu*s* simmons*i** (Lynch, 1974)

659 (Fig. 8)

660 *Ischnocnema simmons*i** Lynch, 1974

661 *Oreobates simmons*i**: Caramaschi and Canedo, 2006

662 *Lynchiu*s* simmons*i**: Padial et al., 2012

663

664 **Holotype**.—KU 147068, young female from Río Piuntza, Cordillera del Cóndor,
 665 Provincia Morona-Santiago, Ecuador, 1830 m, collected by J. E. Simmons and B. MacBryde on
 666 4 January 1972.

667

668 **Diagnosis.**—A moderately large *Lynchius* (SVL of adult females 35.0–40.1 mm, n = 4;
669 adult male 28.3 mm; Table 5) characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and
670 limbs covered with uniformly sized spicule-like warts, which are larger in males than in females;
671 warts on flanks slightly flatter than those of dorsum; occipital folds absent; middorsal fold
672 present on head of females and along head and body of males; dorsolateral folds absent; venter
673 areolate, discoidal fold present; (2) tympanic membrane and annulus distinct, its length 54–57%
674 of eye length; supratympanic fold low, covering upper-posterior margin of tympanic annulus;
675 postrictal tubercles present; (3) head large, as wide as long; snout short, round to nearly truncate
676 in dorsal view and rounded in lateral view; canthus rostralis weakly concave in dorsal view;
677 loreal region concave; lips not flared; (4) cranial crests absent; upper eyelid covered by same
678 spicule-like warts as in dorsum; (5) dentigerous process of vomers large, situated posteromedial
679 to choanae, each process bearing 4–8 teeth; (6) males with small vocal slits and no nuptial pads;
680 (7) hands with long and slender fingers, first finger longer than second; subarticular tubercles
681 large, prominent, conical; supernumerary tubercles large, prominent, round to conical, smaller
682 than subarticular tubercles; skin on palmar surface covered by small, round warts; tips of fingers
683 narrowly rounded, lacking pads and circumferential grooves; fingers with keel-like lateral
684 fringes; (8) ulnar tubercles absent; (9) palmar tubercle prominent, bifid distally, with inner
685 subunit larger than outer; thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length 45–49% SVL,
686 lateral fringes present, webbing absent; Toe III longer than Toe V; Toe III usually reaching
687 midpoint of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV, Toe V reaching or nearly reaching proximal
688 border of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV; subarticular tubercles prominent, conical;
689 supernumerary tubercles present; tips of toes narrowly rounded, lacking pads and circumferential
690 grooves; (11) inner metatarsal tubercle elongate, prominent; outer metatarsal tubercle smaller,

691 round, prominent; subarticular tubercles prominent, conical; supernumerary tubercles smaller
692 than subarticular tubercles; (12) heel and tarsal tubercles absent; (13) in life, dorsum brownish
693 black to black, with or without dark brown marks (interorbital bar, occipital and sacral blotches);
694 venter brown with small cream flecks; iris black with minute light blue spots and an orange
695 circumpupilar ring; in preservative, dorsal coloration dark brown to black with or without diffuse
696 brown areas (interocular bar, dorsal blotches), face with two or three diffuse labial bars and with
697 or without small white spots; throat, chest, and belly pale brown to brown with small cream
698 flecks.

699
700 **Variation.**—The specimens revised herein differ in some aspects from those described
701 by Lynch (1974). Lynch (1974) mentioned the presence of a short sagittal interocular ridge; the
702 trait is present in all females, but the only male known (QCAZ 41640) has a middorsal ridge that
703 extends along the head and body. Low discoidal and supratympanic folds are evident in all
704 examined specimens (reported as absent by Lynch 1974). Finally, most specimens have a black
705 dorsal coloration without evident dorsal marks. In the holotype description, Lynch (1974)
706 mentioned that the dorsum is brownish black with diffuse brown areas (interocular bar, blotches
707 on back) in preservative; this description is accurate for one of the newly collected specimens
708 (QCAZ 30828), but the other three specimens present an almost solid black dorsum (Fig. 8).

709
710 **Distribution and ecology.**—*Lynchius simmonsii* was only known from the type locality.
711 Here we report the finding of two additional populations along the Cordillera del Cóndor
712 (Provincia Zamora-Chinchiipe, Ecuador): Cóndor Mirador (03°18'25"S, 78°23'36"W, 1850 m),

713 and Alto Miazzi (04°15'23.6"S, 78°37'20.8"W, 1300 m) (Fig. 3). This species probably occurs in
 714 adjacent Peru.

715

716 **Remarks.**—*Lynchius simmonsii* was first described by Lynch (1974) based on two
 717 specimens, a juvenile female (KU 147068, holotype) and a juvenile from the same locality (KU
 718 147069). No other information on *L. simmonsii* had been reported ever since. The diagnosis
 719 provided herein is based on the type material, three adult females (QCAZ 30828, 30829, 41639),
 720 and one adult male (QCAZ 41640) from Cordillera del Cóndor.

721

722 *Lynchius tabaconas* sp. nov.

723 (Figs. 9, 10, 11)

724

725 **Holotype.**—MHNC 8637, an adult female from Quebrada del Vino (NSTN), District
 726 Tabaconas, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 2745 m (5°09'53.31"S,
 727 79°12'4.56"W), collected by J.C. Chaparro, on 16 October 2009 (Figure 9, 10, 11A–B).

728

729 **Paratype.**—MHNC 8650, an adult male, from Quebrada del Vino (NSTN), District
 730 Tabaconas, Province San Ignacio, Department of Cajamarca, Peru, 3115 m (5°10'9.65"S,
 731 79°12'26.89"W), collected by J.C. Chaparro, on 17 October 2009 (Fig. 11C–D).

732

733 **Referred specimen.**—MHNC 8649 from the same locality and data of the holotype.

734

735 **Diagnosis.**—A small *Lynchius* (SVL of adult female 28.5 mm; adult male 18.6 mm;

736 Table 6), characterized as follows: (1) skin on dorsum of head, body, and limbs shagreen, with

737 few scattered tubercles; occipital folds absent; middorsal fold complete; dorsolateral folds
738 present, complete; venter smooth; posterior ventral region of thighs coarsely areolate; groin
739 smooth; discoidal fold present posteriorly, weak; thoracic fold absent; (2) tympanic membrane
740 and annulus distinct, its diameter 48–58% of eye diameter; supratympanic fold poorly defined;
741 postrictal tubercles present; (3) head slightly longer than wide (HW/HL 0.9–1.0); snout broadly
742 rounded in dorsal view, short and rounded in lateral profile; canthus rostralis weakly concave in
743 dorsal view; (4) cranial crests absent; upper eyelid bearing few minute tubercles; (5) dentigerous
744 process of vomers prominent, slightly oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae, each process
745 bearing 5 or 6 teeth; (6) males lacking vocal slits and nuptial pads; (7) hands with slender
746 fingers, first finger longer than second; subarticular tubercles prominent, round; supernumerary
747 tubercles round, smaller than subarticular tubercles; tips of fingers narrowly round; pads,
748 circumferential grooves, lateral fringes, and hand webbing absent; (8) ulnar tubercle absent; (9)
749 palmar tubercle undivided, rounded; thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical; (10) foot length about
750 45% SVL; lateral fringes and foot webbing absent; Toe III longer than Toe V; Toe III usually
751 reaching middle of second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV, Toe V reaching proximal border of
752 second subarticular tubercle of Toe IV; subarticular tubercles low, round; supernumerary
753 tubercles absent; tips of toes narrowly rounded, lacking pads and circumferential grooves; (11)
754 inner metatarsal tubercle elongate; outer metatarsal tubercle round, about the same size as inner;
755 subarticular tubercles round, low; supernumerary tubercles absent; (12) heel and tarsal tubercles
756 absent; (13) in life, dorsum of head, body, and limbs dark green with reddish-brown tubercles;
757 canthus rostralis slightly darker than dorsum; middorsal stripe and dorsal surface of forelimbs
758 reddish brown; males with transversal black bars on flanks, hind limbs, and groin; throat grayish
759 brown with white and yellow mottling; belly grayish brown, female with dense yellow blotches

760 and male with white and yellow mottling; ventral surfaces of limbs grayish brown with yellow
761 blotches; yellow blotches also present on axillary region and groin; iris cooper or cooper with
762 greenish border. In preservative, dorsum and dorsal surfaces of limbs grayish brown; middorsal
763 stripe cream; flanks light brown with lighter spots; throat light brown with cream mottling; belly
764 grayish brown, yellow blotches and mottling cream.

765

766 **Comparisons.**—*Lynchius tabaconas* differs from all other species of *Lynchius* by having
767 the unique combination of: dorsum with complete dorsolateral folds; presence of discoidal fold
768 and absence of thoracic fold; tympanic membrane and annulus distinct; no cranial crests; absence
769 of lateral fringes and webbing on fingers and toes; ventral surfaces, axillary region, and groin
770 with cream blotches and/or cream mottling; dorsum dark green with reddish-brown tubercles and
771 middorsal stripe; and yellow blotches and/or mottling on venter. It differs from *Lynchius*
772 *flavomaculatus* (characters of this and other species in parentheses) by its smaller size (SVL of
773 females 34.6–44.2 mm; males 24.0–35.2 mm) and by lacking cranial crests (present). From *L.*
774 *nebulanastes* and *L. parkeri*, it differs by having tympanum distinct (indistinct), lacking
775 supernumerary tubercles (present), and having yellow blotches and/or mottling on venter
776 (absent). *Lynchius tabaconas* differs from *L. simmonsii* by its smaller size (SVL of females 35.0–
777 40.1 mm; male 28.3 mm), having rounded plantar tubercles (conical), skin on dorsum shagreen
778 with scattered tubercles (dorsum covered with uniform-sized spicule-like warts), dorsolateral
779 folds (absent), lateral fringes on fingers and toes absent (present), and yellow blotches and/or
780 mottling on venter (absent). From *Lynchius oblitus* it differs by lacking occipital folds, folds on
781 middorsum, and cranial crests (present).

782

783 **Description of holotype.**—Head as long as wide (HW/HL =1.0); snout rounded in dorsal
784 view and in lateral profile; nostrils slightly protuberant, oriented laterally; canthus rostralis
785 weakly concave in dorsal view, round in frontal profile; loreal region concave; lips not flared;
786 upper eyelid with few small tubercles; cranial crests absent. Supratympanic fold indistinct;
787 tympanic membrane and annulus weakly distinct; tympanic membrane nearly round, its length
788 less than half of eye length; two small postrictal tubercles. Choanae not concealed by palatal
789 shelf of the maxillary arch when roof of mouth is viewed from below; choanae small, round,
790 separated by distance equal to six times the diameter of choana; dentigerous process of vomers
791 prominent, oblique, situated posteromedial to choanae (posterior margin at level of choanae),
792 their width about three times the diameter of choanae, bearing 5 or 6 vomerine teeth. Ulnar
793 tubercle absent; palmar tubercle undivided, rounded; thenar tubercle prominent, elliptical;
794 subarticular tubercles round, prominent, larger than supernumerary tubercles; finger tips
795 narrowly rounded; pads and circumferential grooves absent; fingers lacking lateral fringes and
796 webbing; relative length of fingers: I>II<III>IV. Toes slender (foot length 46% of SVL); heel
797 and tarsus lacking tubercles or folds; inner metatarsal tubercle oval, prominent, about the same
798 size as outer metatarsal tubercle; outer metatarsal tubercle round, low; toes lacking lateral fringes
799 and webbing; toe tips narrowly rounded; pads and circumferential grooves absent; relative length
800 of toes I<II<III>V<IV; Toe V reaching proximal margin of second subarticular tubercle of Toe
801 IV, and Toe III reaching its middle. Skin of dorsum and limbs shagreen with scattered tubercles;
802 ventral surfaces smooth; thighs coarsely areolate posteriorly in ventral view; occipital fold
803 absent; dorsolateral folds present, complete; discoidal fold present; no thoracic fold. In life,
804 dorsum and dorsal surfaces of limbs dark green; a reddish-brown middorsal stripe extending
805 along posterior surface of thigh and shank, here becoming lighter, and reaching plantar surface;

806 head as dorsum, canthus rostralis slightly darker. Throat grayish brown with yellow spots; belly
 807 gray with dense yellow blotches; ventral surfaces of limbs grayish brown with yellow blotches;
 808 yellow blotches also present on axillary region and groin. In preservative, dorsum and dorsal
 809 surfaces of limbs grayish brown; middorsal stripe cream; flanks light brown with lighter spots;
 810 throat light brown, belly grayish brown with cream blotches and spots.

811

812 **Variation.**—According to a single female and a single male collected, females are larger
 813 than males (Table 6). In life, the male had dark ventral surfaces mottled with yellow and white,
 814 and black bars on flanks, groin, and hind limbs (absent in the female).

815

816 **Etymology.**—The specific epithet “tabaconas” refers to the area of the type locality,
 817 Tabaconas Namballe National Sanctuary, which was established in 1988 to protect the
 818 biodiversity and the role of the paramo ecosystem in the Cordillera de Huacabamba.

819

820 **Distribution and ecology.**—This species is only known from the type locality in the
 821 sector of Namballe inside Tabaconas Namballe National Sanctuary, in an area between 2960–
 822 3115 m, within the ecotone between the dwarf forest or montane evergreen forest from northern
 823 Andes (above 2700 m) and paramo from northern Andes (above 3100 m, Fig. 3). Specimens
 824 were found above the ground of forests, and captured through pitfall traps in the paramo. The
 825 new species occurs in sympatry with *Gastrotheca monticola*, *Pristimantis bustamante*, *P.*
 826 *schultei*, and *Lynchius oblitus*. See more details about vegetation in Chaparro et al. (2012).

827

828

- 829 1. Skin of dorsum covered with uniformly-sized spicule-like warts; palmar and plantar tubercles
830 conical: *L. simmonsii*
- 831 Skin of dorsum shagreen, with scattered tubercles; palmar and plantar tubercles rounded: step
832 2
- 833 2. Tympanic membrane and annulus distinct (i.e., not differentiated from surrounding skin):
834 step 3
- 835 Tympanic membrane and annulus indistinct, tympanum concealed by skin: step 5
- 836 3. Occipital folds V-shaped; middorsum bearing <->-shaped or w-shaped folds: *L. oblitus*
837 Occipital folds absent; middorsum lacking folds: step 4
- 838 4. Large (SVL of adult females 34.6–44.2 mm; adult males 24.0–35.2 mm); cranial crests
839 present; males with vocal slits: *L. flavomaculatus*
- 840 Small (SVL of adult female 28.5 mm; adult male 18.6 mm); cranial crests absent; males
841 lacking vocal slits: *L. tabaconas*
- 842 5. Legs long (TB/SVL, TH/SVL, and FL/SVL 0.5–0.6); upper eyelid covered by small scattered
843 tubercles; frontoparietals not rugose: *L. nebulanastes*
- 844 Legs short (TB/SVL, TH/SVL, and FL/SVL 0.4–0.5); upper eyelid not covered by small
845 scattered tubercles; frontoparietals rugose: *L. parkeri*

846

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DISCUSSION

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The clade formed by ((*Lynchius* + *Oreobates*) *Phrynopus*) constitutes a morphologically and ecologically diverse group of frogs with a broad distribution in South America. The monophyly of these genera, as well as the overall clade, is corroborated by our parsimony and maximum likelihood inferences under two different strategies of alignment. Thus, variation in

852 sampled gene sequences across loci with different evolutionary histories and rates of change (i.e.,
853 coding and non-coding mtDNA and nuDNA genes) provides consistent and strong (resilient to
854 assumptions) evidence for the single and unique origin of this clade and its monophyletic genera.
855 However, several internal relationships as well as the position of several outgroup taxa differ
856 between analyses. Whether these differences are definitively determined by the different
857 assumptions of methods, or whether these assumptions are sensible to evidence (taxon and
858 character sampling), is a matter to be decided by future analyses with increasing character and
859 taxon sampling. However, the latter hypothesis has received support by recent studies, reporting
860 increasingly congruent relationships between maximum likelihood and parsimony analyses
861 (under tree-alignment) when additional taxa and characters were sampled (e.g., Padial et al.
862 2014; Castroviejo et al. 2015).

863 The phylogenetic framework provided by our analyses, which include all taxa described
864 for *Lynchius*, almost all *Oreobates*, and almost half of *Phrynopus* species, constitutes a good
865 starting point for testing different scenarios of diversification and character evolution in the
866 Neotropics. Although it is not the goal of the present study to test biogeographic hypotheses or
867 the variety of evolutionary hypotheses that can be proposed based on observed patterns of
868 morphological variation and geographical distribution in light of phylogeny, we provide below
869 an overview of patterns and outline several possible scenarios that could be subjects of future
870 studies.

871 First of all, the molecular perspective on the affinities of *Lynchius*, *Oreobates*, and
872 *Phrynopus* provided by this study is considerably different from the scenario constructed on the
873 basis of external morphology and osteology, and involves a more complex biogeographic history
874 and a new interpretation of morphological variation. For example, all but the two new species of

875 *Lynchius* and *L. simmonsii* were considered part of the genus *Phrynopus* as defined by Lynch
876 (1975), due to their overall similarity — knob-shaped phalanges, chubby bodies, short
877 extremities, inconspicuous plantar tubercles, and narrow heads. Also, *L. simmonsii* was until very
878 recently considered part of *Oreobates* and was initially described as an *Ischnocnema* (Lynch
879 1974) — when *Ischnocnema* was considered a broadly distributed genus that included most
880 species of what is now *Oreobates* (see Caramaschi and Canedo 2006) — due to its tuberculate
881 skin, broad head with large eyes, slender extremities with large and conical plantar tubercles and
882 long fingers, and toes lacking expanded discs. Furthermore, with the transfer of *Phrynopus*
883 *ayacucho* Lehr, 2007 and *Phrynopus pereger* Lynch, 1975 to *Oreobates*, and the transfer of
884 *Oreobates simmonsii* (Lynch, 1974) to *Lynchius*, putative morphological synapomorphies for the
885 three genera have vanished, such as the presence of conical plantar tubercles (as proposed for
886 *Oreobates*; Padial et al. 2007), or the knobbed versus t-shaped terminal phalanges (as proposed
887 for *Phrynopus*; Lynch 1975; Trueb and Lehr 2008). Also, Trueb and Lehr (2008) described a
888 number of characters purportedly distinguishing *Lynchius*, *Oreobates*, and *Phrynopus*, such as
889 the lack of dentigerous processes of the vomers in *Phrynopus*, the presence of cranial crests in
890 *Lynchius*, and the extraordinarily large medial and lateral process of premaxillae in *Lynchius* and
891 *Phrynopus* in comparison to *Oreobates*, that turned out to vary within genera. They also pointed
892 out at multiple differences in composite characters (e.g., the relative length of the cultriform
893 process with respect to the orbit, or the relative length of fingers) that still need to be reduced to
894 independent transformation series in order to be tested as synapomorphies (Grant and Kluge
895 2004). A comprehensive analysis of the external and internal anatomy of *Lynchius*, *Oreobates*,
896 and *Phrynopus*, and the phylogenetic analysis of resulting characters, is still needed to reach an
897 adequate understanding of the origin of morphological variation in these clades. Fortunately,

898 ongoing studies of the internal anatomy of terraranas (e.g., Taboada et al. 2014) is leading to the
899 discovery of synapomorphies at different levels, and increasing taxon and character sampling
900 will probably lead to further discoveries and a better picture of morphological character variation
901 across clades.

902 *Lynchius* and *Phrynopus* have relatively small, and ecologically restricted distributions in
903 the high Andes and, as mentioned above, most species in these two clades present a number of
904 external and osteological similarities (see Lynch 1975; Trueb and Lehr 2008). All species of
905 *Lynchius* and *Phrynopus* are Andean and terrestrial, but while *Lynchius simmonsii* — the sister
906 group of the rests of *Lynchius* — occurs in montane forest below 2000 m, all other *Lynchius* and
907 *Phrynopus* inhabit cloud and elfin forests above 2200 m. The high Andean species in both
908 *Lynchius* and *Phrynopus* are overall short legged, have rounded bodies, narrow heads, short
909 extremities, short digits with knobbed, rather than t-shaped, terminal phalanges that lack
910 expanded toepads. These similarities among high altitude species led Lynch (1975) and
911 subsequent authors to deduce a single origin for these similar traits, but our analyses support
912 instead that *Phrynopus* and *Lynchius* are not closely related and, hence, that similar traits evolved
913 independently as the result of independent histories that might be connected to adaptation to
914 similar environments.

915 The genus *Oreobates* presents a broader diversity in anatomical traits and distribution
916 that encompasses a diverse number of South American ecoregions. Only two species of
917 *Oreobates* (*O. ayacucho* and *O. pereger*) occur in the high Andean humid grasslands (i.e., wet
918 puna ecoregion, as this habitat is named in southern and central Peru; Olson et al. 2001), while
919 most other species occur in montane forests of the eastern slopes of the Andes between 1000 and
920 3000 m elevation. There are, nonetheless, several species inhabiting warmer environments such

921 as the Amazon lowlands (e.g., *O. cruralis* and *O. quixensis*), the Cerrado (*O. crepitans* and *O.*
922 *heterodactylus*; Padial et al. 2012), and the dry Atlantic forests of eastern Brazil (*O. remotus*;
923 Teixeira et al. 2012). Also, several species have colonized the highly seasonal inter-Andean dry
924 valleys (e.g., *O. ibischi*, Reichle et al. 2001; *O. berdemenos*, Pereyra et al. 2014), and the Yungas
925 of northern Argentina (*O. barituensis*; Vaira and Ferrari 2008). Interestingly, the two terrestrial
926 species from the high Andean grasslands (*O. ayacucho* and *O. pereger*) resemble *Lynchius* and
927 *Phrynopus* and were indeed considered part of *Phrynopus* (Lynch 1975). As such, the
928 independent evolution of similar traits in *O. ayacucho* and *O. pereger* further support the
929 hypothesis that the adaptation to high altitude environments of the Andes led to similar
930 transformations of traits in *Lynchius*, *Oreobates*, and *Phrynopus*. This pattern is further
931 supported by the similar morphologies of other high Andean genera, such as *Bryophryne*,
932 *Niceforonia*, and *Psychrophrynella* that were also formerly considered part of *Phrynopus*.

933 Traits of species inhabiting other environments also support the idea that convergent
934 evolution is behind several of the observed recurrent patterns of morphological variation. For
935 example, species from more xeric habitats such as Cerrado (*O. crepitans*, *O. heterodactylus*) or
936 the inter-Andean dry valleys (*O. ibischi*, *O. discoidalis*), which often perch on low vegetation
937 and are slender and present long extremities with T-shaped terminal phalanges and large discs on
938 fingers and toes, were formerly associated to more arboreal genera such as *Eleutherodactylus*
939 (Lynch 1989; Lynch and Duellman 1997) and *Pristimantis* (Hedges et al. 2008). Molecular
940 phylogenetic analyses indicate instead that similarity is the result of independent evolutionary
941 histories (e.g., Canedo and Haddad 2012; Hedges et al. 2008; Padial et al. 2014). Likewise, the
942 similarity between species of *Oreobates* from montane forests and the Amazon lowlands to
943 *Lynchius simmonsii* and some species of *Ischnocnema* (i.e., tuberculate skins, long extremities

944 and large heads, conical plantar tubercles, lack of expanded finger and toe discs) also suggests
945 the possibility of convergent evolution as the result of adaptation to the conditions of the forest
946 floor of tropical forests. These are nonetheless hypotheses deduced from raw observation of
947 patterns in light of the relationships inferred in this study and that obviously require further
948 testing.

949 Inferred relationships and distribution patterns also point out at obvious biogeographical
950 connections. For example, the relationships of *Oreobates* support an Atlantic Forest-Andean
951 connection through the Cerrado and/or Amazonia, as indicated by the close relationship between
952 *O. remotus*, *O. crepitans* and *O. heterodactylus* (dry Atlantic Forest and Cerrado species), with
953 Amazonian (*O. cruralis*) and Andean species (*O. berdemenos*, *O. discoidalis*, *O. ibischi*, and *O.*
954 *madidi*). This biogeographic connection is also supported by the distribution and relationships of
955 *Barycholos*, with one species in the Cerrado and one in the Pacific versant of the Andes, and has
956 recently been supported for marsupial frogs (Blackburn and Duellman 2013; Teixeira et al. 2012;
957 Castroviejo et al. 2015). Also, it seems that species diversity of the clade formed by *Lynchius*,
958 *Oreobates*, and *Phrynopus*, is concentrated in the Andes. The position of some lowland/montane
959 forest taxa such as *O. quixensis* and *O. saxatilis* in *Oreobates* as a sister group that is sister to the
960 rest of the species in the genus (Padial et al. 2012), and of the montane species *L. simmonsii* as
961 the sister group of the remaining species of *Lynchius*, indicates a montane forest origin of the
962 high Andean anurans; this is a quite reasonable hypothesis that will nevertheless need to be
963 tested.

964 At last, it is worth pointing out again that phylogenetic, anatomical, and biogeographical
965 patterns discussed above confront the problem of underestimated species numbers. Three
966 candidate species of *Oreobates* reported by Padial et al. (2012) remain to be named, one from the

967 dry inter-Andean valleys of central Bolivia, one from the Yungas of Cochabamba (Bolivia), and
968 one from montane forests in southern Peru. Four other species of *Oreobates* have been recently
969 discovered in Peru, one in the montane forests of eastern Loreto, one in the mountain forest of
970 central Cusco, one from dry forest from eastern Apurimac, and one from inter-Andean dry
971 forests in central Peru; all those species remain to be named (J.C. Chaparro, personal
972 communication). The pace of species discovery in recent years also provides a glimpse of the
973 rapidly growing understanding of species diversity with the exploration of new areas and the
974 study of available collections. As many as 17 species of *Phrynopus* have been discovered during
975 the last ten years, and ongoing surveys in central Peru are revealing further new species (E. Lehr,
976 personal observation). Twelve species of *Oreobates* have been named during the same period
977 (see Padial et al. 2012 and references therein) and many areas of the Andes and the Amazon
978 suitable for the existence of species in this group remain to be surveyed. *Lynchius* has received
979 far less attention than these last two groups and, yet, surveys in a relatively small area revealed
980 two non-sister species segregated altitudinally (the ones described herein), indicating that more
981 species could await discovery in the many areas of the Cordillera de Huancabamba, Cordillera
982 Oriental, and Cordillera del Cóndor. Overall, field surveys and taxonomic work are still largely
983 insufficient at this time and for a region that extends for thousands of kilometers along the Andes
984 and the adjacent lowlands; this fact precludes access to accurate data that are needed for rigorous
985 empirical analyses of biodiversity patterns and evolutionary history.

986

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1013

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- 1172 APPENDIX I
- 1173 Specimens Examined
- 1174 *Lynchius flavomaculatus*: ECUADOR: Loja: 13–14 km E Loja, 2850 m, KU 119721–24; 8–9 km
 1175 N San Lucas, 3000 m, KU 119737–42, 121354; 10 km S Saraguro, KU 142201–02; 19.4
 1176 km S Yangana, KU 218210. Morona-Santiago: FMNH 197838, 197846, USNM 98929–
 1177 30, 195393–424, 260788; 28 km SW Plan de Milagro, KU 202654–55. Zamora-
 1178 Chinchipe: 15 km E Loja, 2700 m, BMNH 1947.2.16.11 (holotype), 1947.2.16.12–14
 1179 (paratypes); KU 119716–20, 119725–36, 119743 (cleared and stained), 141474–77,
 1180 142198–200, 165955–67, 166294 (cleared and stained), 202656.
- 1181 *Lynchius nebulanastes*: PERU: Piura: El Tambo, 31.5 km E Canchaque, 2770 m, KU 181407
 1182 (holotype), 181392–406, 181408–14 (paratype), 181415–16 (cleared and stained),
 1183 181841, 219806–819.
- 1184 *Lynchius oblitus*: PERU: Cajamarca: Santuario Nacional Tabaconas Namballe: MHNC 8598,
 1185 8599, 8601, 8602, 8606, 8614, 8625, 8626, 8652, 8672, 8673, 8674, 8675, 8676, 8677,
 1186 8689, 8690, MTD 45954.
- 1187 *Lynchius parkeri*: PERU: Piura: FLMNH 34092–108; Cordillera between Chanchaque
 1188 (=Canchaque) and Huancabamba, KU 135278 (holotype), 135279–311 (paratypes),
 1189 135306 (cleared and stained); El Tambo, 31.5 km E Chanchaque, 2770 m, KU 181288–
 1190 91, 181393, 219820; 25 km SW Huancabamba, KU 181292–356, 181823, 181824
 1191 (cleared and stained), 181825–27, 181828 (cleared and stained), 181829, 196581–91,
 1192 LSU 32172–32239.

- 1193 *Lynchius simmonsii*: ECUADOR: Morona-Santiago: Río Piuntza, Cordillera del Cóndor, 1830 m,
1194 KU 147068 (holotype), 147069 (paratype); Zamora-Chinchiipe: Cordillera del Cóndor,
1195 Cóndor Mirador, 1850 m, QCAZ 30829–30; Miazzi Alto, 1300 m, QCAZ 41639–40.
- 1196 *Lynchius tabaconas*: PERU: Cajamarca: Santuario Nacional Tabaconas Namballe, MHNC 8637,
1197 8649, 8650.
- 1198
- 1199

APPENDIX II

1200

1201 GenBank accession numbers for loci and terminals of species sampled in this study.

	12S	16S	RAG	TYR
<i>Barycholos pulcher</i>	EU186727	EU186709	EU186744	EU186765
<i>Barycholos ternetzi</i>	-	DQ283094	-	JX267680
<i>Bryophryne cophites</i>	EF493537	EF493537	EF493423	EF493508
<i>Euparkerella brasiliensis</i>	JX267390	JX267468	JX267545	JX267682
<i>Haddadus binotatus</i>	EF493361	EF493361	EF493397	DQ282918
<i>Holoaden bradei</i>	EF493378	EF493366	EF493449	EU186779
<i>Holoaden luederwaldti</i>	EU186728	EU186710	JX267549	EU186768
<i>Hypodactylus brunneus</i>	EF493357	EF493357	EF493422	EF493484
<i>Hypodactylus dolops</i>	EF493394	EF493394	EF493414	EF493483
<i>Lynchius flavomaculatus</i>	EU186667	EU186667	EU186745	EU186766
<i>Lynchius nebulanastes</i>	EU186704	EU186704	-	-
<i>Lynchius parkeri</i>	EU186667	EU186705	-	-
<i>Lynchius simmonsii</i>	JF809940	JF810004	JF809915	JF809894
<i>Noblella heyeri</i>	JX267463	JX267541	-	-
<i>Noblella lochites</i>	EU186699	EU186699	EU186756	EU186777
<i>Noblella myrmecoides</i>	JX267464	JX267542	-	-
<i>Oreobates amarakaeri</i>	JF809934	JF809996	JF809913	JF809891
<i>Oreobates ayacucho</i>	JF809933	JF809970	JF809912	JF809890
<i>Oreobates barituensis</i>	JF809935	JF809999	JF809914	JF809892
<i>Oreobates berdemenos</i>	KJ125511	KJ125507	-	-

<i>Oreobates choristolemma</i>	JF809921	FJ539067	JF809900	JF809881
<i>Oreobates crepitans</i>	-	KJ125510	-	-
<i>Oreobates cruralis</i>	EU186666	EU186666	EU186743	EU186764
<i>Oreobates discoidalis</i>	JF809925	FJ539068	JF809904	JF809884
<i>Oreobates gemcare</i>	JF809930	JF809960	JF809909	-
<i>Oreobates granulosus</i>	JF809929	EU368897	JF809908	JF809887
<i>Oreobates heterodactylus</i>	JF809923	EU192296	JF809902	JF809882
<i>Oreobates ibischi</i>	FJ438817	FJ438806	-	-
<i>Oreobates lehri</i>	JF809927	JF809957	JF809906	-
<i>Oreobates lundbergi</i>	JF809928	JF809958	JF809907	JF809886
<i>Oreobates machiguenga</i>	JF809932	JF809969	JF809911	JF809889
<i>Oreobates madidi</i>	JF809922	FJ539070	JF809901	-
<i>Oreobates pereger</i>	JF809926	JF809958	JF809905	JF809885
<i>Oreobates quixensis</i>	EF493828	EF493662	-	JF809893
<i>Oreobates remotus</i>	-	JN688275	-	-
<i>Oreobates sanctaegrucis</i>	JF809924	JF809951	JF809903	JF809883
<i>Oreobates sanderi</i>	-	EU368904	-	-
<i>Oreobates saxatilis</i>	JF809931	EU186708	JF809910	JF809888
<i>Phrynopus auriculatus</i>	EF493708	EF493708	-	-
<i>Phrynopus barthlenae</i>	AM039721	AM039649	-	-
<i>Phrynopus bracki</i>	EF493709	EF493709	EF493421	EF493507
<i>Phrynopus bufoides</i>	AM039713	AM039645	-	-
<i>Phrynopus heimorum</i>	AM039704	AM039636	-	-

<i>Phrynopus horstpauli</i>	AM039715	AM039651	-	-
<i>Phrynopus juninensis</i>	AM039725	AM039657	-	-
<i>Phrynopus kauneorum</i>	AM039718	AM039650	-	-
<i>Phrynopus pesantesi</i>	AM039724	AM039656	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tautzorum</i>	AM039720	AM039652	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tribulosus</i>	EU186725	EU186707	-	-
<i>Psychrophrynella guillei</i>	AY843720	AY843720	-	DQ282995
<i>Psychrophrynella usurpator</i>	EF493714	EF493714	EU186762	EU186780
<i>Psychrophrynella wettsteini</i>	EU186696	EU186696	EU186755	EU186776

1202

	28S	CYTB	HH3	POMC
<i>Barycholos pulcher</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Barycholos ternetzi</i>	DQ283496	JX298401	DQ284144	JX298136
<i>Bryophryne cophites</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Euparkerella brasiliensis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Haddadus binotatus</i>	DQ283493	GQ345198	DQ284142	GQ345259
<i>Holoaden bradei</i>	-	JX298403	-	JX298138
<i>Holoaden luederwaldti</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Hypodactylus brunneus</i>	GQ345138	GQ345203	GQ345218	GQ345264
<i>Hypodactylus dolops</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Lynchius flavomaculatus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Lynchius nebulanastes</i>	-	-	-	AY819154
<i>Lynchius parkeri</i>	-	-	-	-

<i>Lynchius simmonsii</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella heyeri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella lochites</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella myrmecoides</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates amarakaeri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates ayacucho</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates barituensis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates berdemenos</i>	-	KJ125511	-	-
<i>Oreobates choristolemma</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates crepitans</i>	-	KJ125512	-	-
<i>Oreobates cruralis</i>	-	EU368881	-	-
<i>Oreobates discoidalis</i>	-	EU368883	-	-
<i>Oreobates gemcare</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates granulosis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates heterodactylus</i>	-	EU368885	-	-
<i>Oreobates ibischi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates lehri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates lundbergi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates machiguenga</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates madidi</i>	-	EU368887	-	-
<i>Oreobates pereger</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates quixensis</i>	-	EU368889	-	AY819093
<i>Oreobates remotus</i>	-	JN688276	-	-

<i>Oreobates sanctaecrucis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates sanderi</i>	-	EU368891	-	-
<i>Oreobates saxatilis</i>	-	-	DQ284091	-
<i>Phrynopus auriculatus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus barthlenae</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus bracki</i>	GQ345137	GQ345202	GQ345217	GQ345263
<i>Phrynopus bufoides</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus heimorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus horstpauli</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus juninensis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus kauneorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus pesantesi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tautzorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tribulosus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Psychrophrynella guillei</i>	AY844323	-	DQ284371	-
<i>Psychrophrynella usurpator</i>	-	GQ345205	-	-
<i>Psychrophrynella wettsteini</i>	GQ345139	-	GQ345219	GQ345266

1203

	CMYC-EX2	CMYC-EX3	RHO	SIA
<i>Barycholos pulcher</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Barycholos ternetzi</i>	-	-	DQ283810	-
<i>Bryophryne cophites</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Euparkerella brasiliensis</i>	-	-	-	-

<i>Haddadus binotatus</i>	GQ345147	GQ345165	DQ283807	GQ345309
<i>Holoaden bradei</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Holoaden luederwaldti</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Hypodactylus brunneus</i>	GQ345151	-	-	GQ345315
<i>Hypodactylus dolops</i>	-	-	GQ345304	-
<i>Lynchius flavomaculatus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Lynchius nebulanastes</i>	AY819320	-	-	-
<i>Lynchius parkeri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Lynchius simmonsii</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella heyeri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella lochites</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Noblella myrmecoides</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates amarakaeri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates ayacucho</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates barituensis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates berdemenos</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates choristolemma</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates crepitans</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates cruralis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates discoidalis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates gemcare</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates granulosis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates heterodactylus</i>	-	-	-	-

<i>Oreobates ibischi</i>	AY211288	AY211288	-	-
<i>Oreobates lehri</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates lundbergi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates machiguenga</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates madidi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates pereger</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates quixensis</i>	AY819178	AY819257	-	-
<i>Oreobates remotus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates sanctaecrucis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates sanderi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Oreobates saxatilis</i>	-	-	DQ283788	DQ282661
<i>Phrynopus auriculatus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus barthlenae</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus bracki</i>	GQ345150	GQ345168	GQ345303	GQ345314
<i>Phrynopus bufoides</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus heimorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus horstpauli</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus juninensis</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus kauneorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus pesantesi</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tautzorum</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Phrynopus tribulosus</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Psychrophrynella guillei</i>	-	-	-	-

<i>Psychrophrynella usurpator</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Psychrophrynella wettsteini</i>	GQ345153	-	-	GQ345316

1204

1205

1206 TABLE 1.—Sequences of *Lynchius* produced in this study. All voucher specimens are from Santuario Nacional Tabaconas-Namballe,
 1207 Cajamarca, Peru (5°13'45.5"S, 79°17'13.2"W).

	Voucher	DNA collection	GenBank				
	(MHNC)	(MNCN-DNA)	12S	16S	POMC	RAG	TYR
<i>Lynchius oblitus</i>	8614	48820	KX470776	KX470783	-	KX470792	KX470799
<i>Lynchius oblitus</i>	8652	48806	KX470775	KX470782	-	KX470791	KX470798
<i>Lynchius oblitus</i>	8674	48823	KX470777	KX470784	-	KX470793	KX470800
<i>Lynchius oblitus</i>	8676	48824	KX470778	KX470785	-	KX470794	KX470801
<i>Lynchius oblitus</i>	8677	48825	KX470779	KX470786	-	KX470795	KX470802
<i>Lynchius tabaconas</i>	8637	48795	KX470773	KX470780	KX470787	KX470789	KX470796
<i>Lynchius tabaconas</i>	8650	48804	KX470774	KX470781	KX470788	KX470790	KX470797

1208

1209 TABLE 2.—Sequence primers used in this study.

Locus	Primer name and priming region (5'-3')	Source
16S	16Sar: CGCCTGTTTATCAAAAACAT 16Sbr: CCGGTCTGAACTCAGATCACGT	Hillis et al. (1996)
16S	16L19: AATACCTAACGAACTTAGCGATAGCTGGTT 16H24: TACCTTCGCACGGTTAGKRTACCGCGGCCGTT	Hedges et al. (2008)
16S	16S-JMP-F: CATGGTAAGTRTACCGGAAGGTG 16S-JMP-R: ACCAGCTATDACTAAGTTCG	This study
12S- tRNA _{phe}	12S-t-Phe-frog: ATAGCRCTGAARAYGCTRAGATG 12S-frogRa: TCRATTRYAGGACAGGCTCCTCTAG	Wiens et al. (2005)
12S- tRNA _{val}	12S-t-Val-frog: TGTAAGCGARAGGCTTTKGTTAAGCT 12S-frogFa: CAAACTRGGATTAGATACCCYACTATG	Wiens et al. (2005)
cmyc	cmyc1U: GAGGACATCTGGAARAARTT cmyc3L: GTCTTCCTCTTGTCRTTCTCYTC	Crawford (2003)
POMC	POMC-1: AATGTATYAAAGMMTGCAAGATGGWCCT POMC-2: TAYTGRCCCTTYTTGTGGGCRTT	Wiens et al. (2005)
RAG1	R182: GCCATAACTGCTGGAGCATYAT R270: AGYAGATGTTGCCTGGGTCTTC	Heinicke et al. (2007)
TYR	Tyr1C: GGCAGAGGAWCRTGCCAAGATGT Tyr1G: TGCTGGGCRTCTCTCCARTCCCA	Bossuyt and Milinkovitch (2000)

1210

1211

1212 TABLE 3.—Uncorrected pairwise distances (%) for a fragment of the 16S gene compared among
 1213 species of *Lynchius*.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
(1) <i>Lynchius tabaconas</i> MHNC8637							
(2) <i>Lynchius tabaconas</i> MHNC8650	0.1						
(3) <i>Lynchius oblitus</i> MHNC8652	8.4	8.3					
(4) <i>Lynchius oblitus</i> MHNC8614	7.0	7.0	4.8				
(5) <i>Lynchius oblitus</i> MHNC8677	6.9	7.0	4.4	0.6			
(6) <i>Lynchius flavomaculatus</i>	6.2	6.1	7.8	7.0	7.0		
(7) <i>Lynchius nebulanastes</i>	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.6	8.2	8.5	
(8) <i>Lynchius parkeri</i>	10	9.9	9.6	9.4	8.9	9.2	10.5

1214

1215 TABLE 4.—Morphometrics of *Lynchius oblitus* (in mm). For abbreviations, see Material and
 1216 Methods.

	Females				Male
	MHNC 8674	MHNC 8601	MHNC 8675	MHNC 8677	MTD 45954
SVL	25.5	28.4	24.5	28.3	21.7
HL	9.8	10.7	9.5	10.7	8.4
HW	9.6	10.8	9.7	10.7	8.1
EL	2.8	3.1	2.6	2.8	2.5
EN	2.5	2.7	2.2	2.4	2.0
IND	2.4	2.5	2.2	2.4	2.3
EE	4.2	4.2	3.8	4.3	3.8
TyH	1.6	1.8	1.9	1.5	1.5
TyL	1.6	1.7	1.5	1.2	1.6
F.III	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4
F.IV	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.4
FA	6.2	6.1	5.3	6.3	5.3
TB	10.1	10.8	9.8	10.6	6.2
TH	10.1	11.5	9.4	11.5	9.7
FL	11.5	11.7	10.9	11.6	10.4
T.IV	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4

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1218

1219 TABLE 5—Morphometrics of *Lynchiu*s* simmons*i** (in mm). Not all measurements were available
 1220 for all specimens, see Material and Methods for explanations and abbreviations.

	Females				Male
	KU	QCAZ	QCAZ	QCAZ	QCAZ
	147068	30828	30829	41639	41640
SVL	25.2	36.0	35.0	40.1	28.3
HL	11.1	13.7	14.2	16.5	11.8
HW	10.1	13.8	13.8	16.5	11.6
EL	3.8	4.7	4.4	5.0	4.1
EN	2.3	–	–	–	–
IND	2.2	–	–	–	–
EE	3.7	–	–	–	–
TyH	2.2	–	–	–	–
TyL	1.9	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.3
F.III	–	–	–	–	–
F.IV	–	–	–	–	–
FA	6.7	–	–	–	–
TB	13.9	17.1	16.9	19.5	14.2
TH	13.8	–	–	–	–
FL	14.6	–	–	–	–
T.IV	14.4	17.5	16.9	18.7	12.6

1222 TABLE 6.—Morphometrics of *Lynchius tabaconas* (in mm). For abbreviations, see Material and
 1223 Methods.

	Female	Male
	MHNC 8637	MHNC 8650
SVL	28.5	18.6
HL	10.8	6.8
HW	10.4	6.4
EL	3.2	2.0
EN	3.0	2.0
IND	2.4	1.7
EE	4.4	3.2
TyH	1.8	1.4
TyL	1.5	1.2
F.III	0.5	0.3
F.IV	0.4	0.3
FA	6.1	4.4
TB	12.3	8.6
TH	12.5	8.5
FL	13.2	8.3
T.IV	0.5	0.4

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1227 FIG. 1.—Phylogenetic trees resulting from the analysis of datasets of 7959 aligned bp
 1228 (POY) and 7145 aligned bp (MAFFT) and composed of the mitochondrial genes 12S, 16S, the
 1229 intervening tRNA^{val}, and tRNA^{leu} segments, a fragment of the coding mtDNA gene cytb, and
 1230 fragments of the nuclear protein-coding genes c-myc (exons 2 and 3), POMC, RAG1, and Tyr.
 1231 (A) Maximum parsimony optimal tree of 11,222 transformations depicting the relationships of
 1232 species of *Bryophryne* and other genera of Holodeninae. Numbers above ancestral branches
 1233 indicate Goodman-Bremer values, and those under branches are Jackknife proportions (asterisks
 1234 represent Jackknife values of 100%). (B) Maximum likelihood optimal tree (log likelihood = –
 1235 54289.266) and bootstrap node values.

1236

1237

1238 FIG. 2.—Adult female holotype of *Lynchius flavomaculatus* (BMNH 1947.2.16.11, SVL
 1239 39.4 mm) (A–B), adult female holotype of *L. nebulanastes* (KU 181407, SVL 35.0 mm) (C–D),
 1240 and adult male holotype of *L. parkeri* (KU 135278, SVL 22.2 mm) (E–F).

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1242

1243 FIG. 3.—Geographic distribution of six species of *Lynchius*: *L. flavomaculatus* (circle), *L.*
 1244 *nebulanastes* (square), *L. oblitus* (pentagon), *L. parkeri* (square), *L. simmonsii* (triangle), and *L.*
 1245 *tabaconas* (diamond). Symbols in black represent the type locality of species. Area above 500 m
 1246 in light gray and area above 1000 m in dark gray.

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1248

1249 FIG. 4.—Adult female holotype of *Lynchius oblitus* (MHNC 8674, SVL 25.5 mm) from
1250 Santuario Nacional Tabaconas-Namballe, Cajamarca, Peru, 3300 m (5°13'45.5"S,
1251 79°17'13.2"W). Dorsal (A) and ventral (B) views; lateral view of head (C), hand (D), and foot
1252 (E).

1253

1254 FIG. 5.—*Lynchius oblitus* sp. nov. Ventral views of left hand (A) and right foot (B) of
1255 holotype (MHNC 8674).

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1257

1258 FIG. 6.—Adult female paratype of *Lynchius oblitus* (MHNC 8601) from Santuario
1259 Nacional Tabaconas-Namballe, Cajamarca, Peru, 3300 m (5°13'45.5"S, 79°17'13.2"W). Dorsal
1260 (A) and ventral (B) views. Photo: Nature Consulting SAC.

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1262

1263 FIG. 7.—Skull of *Lynchius parkeri*. (A), KU 135306 in dorsal view (modified from
1264 Lynch, 1975, p. 26, Fig. 10), and (B) a picture of the same skull; note ornamentation in
1265 frontoparietals.

1266

1267

1268 FIG. 8.—Adult female of *Lynchius simmonsii* from Alto Miazi, 1300 m (04°15'23.6"S,
1269 78°37'20.8"W), Zamora-Chinchipec, Ecuador (QCAZ 41639, SVL 40.1 mm). Dorsal (A) and
1270 ventral (C) views; ventral view of left hand (B). Photos: Santiago R. Ron.

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1273 FIG. 9.—Adult female holotype of *Lynchius tabaconas* (MHNC 8637, SVL 28.5 mm)
1274 from Santuario Nacional Tabaconas-Namballe, Cajamarca, Peru, 2745 m (5°09'46.7"S,
1275 79°17'13.2"W). Dorsal (A) and ventral (B) views; lateral view of head (C), hand (D), and foot
1276 (E).

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1279 FIG. 10.—*Lynchius tabaconas* sp. nov. Ventral views of right hand (A) and right foot (B)
1280 of holotype (MHNC 8637).

1281

1282

1283 FIG. 11.—Adult female holotype of *Lynchius tabaconas* (MHNC 8637, SVL 28.5 mm)
1284 (A–B) and adult male paratype of *Lynchius tabaconas* (MHNC 8650, SVL 18.6 mm) (C–D)
1285 from Santuario Nacional Tabaconas-Namballe, Cajamarca, Peru, 2745 m (5°09'46.7"S,
1286 79°17'13.2"W).